

Sexual cycle of the two mussel species cohabiting in the Mirleft Bay (Southern Morocco): *Perna perna* (Linné, 1758) and *Mytilus galloprovincialis* (Lamarck, 1819)

Estudio comparativo del ciclo sexual de dos especies de mejillones que cohabitan en la Bahía de Mirleft (sur de Marruecos): *Perna perna* (Linné, 1758) y *Mytilus galloprovincialis* (Lamarck, 1819)

Asmaa EL KHOU*, Maria BOUKAICI*, Abderrazak KAAAYA* & Abdellatif MOUKRIM*

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ABSTRACT

The goal of our investigation was to study the reproduction of the mussel species *Mytilus galloprovincialis* and *Perna perna* that grow together in the Mirleft Bay (Sidi Ifni, South Morocco). Several parameters of reproductive cycle were monitored at three representative sites (Grizim, Tabougricht and Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdellah) during one annual cycle. In both species, only a small percentage of individuals were found at the sexual resting stage at the three sites. Two spawning periods were observed. Mussel density presented large variations, depending on the month and sites, and correlated with the reproductive cycle and environmental conditions. Our results show that mussels in Mirleft Bay, now exploited by the local population, are suitable for mussel farming development in this area.

RESUMEN

El objetivo de nuestra investigación es estudiar la biología de las dos especies de mejillones que crecen juntas en la bahía Mirleft: *Mytilus galloprovincialis* y *Perna perna*, situada en Sidi Ifni, sur de Marruecos. Se indagaron distintos parámetros del ciclo reproductor en tres sitios de esta zona (Grizim, Tabougricht y Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdellah) durante un ciclo anual. En ambas especies, solamente una pequeña proporción de los individuos fueron encontrados en fase de reposo sexual en los tres sitios. Se observaron dos períodos de desove. La densidad de mejillones presenta amplias variaciones entre meses y entre sitios, correlacionadas con el ciclo reproductor y las condiciones ambientales. Los datos obtenidos en este estudio muestran que los mejillones de la bahía de Mirleft, ahora explotados por la población local, son idóneos para el desarrollo de cultivos de mejillones en esta zona.

INTRODUCTION

The southern Moroccan Atlantic coast is known for its nutrient-rich water due to the upwelling phenome-

non (BINET, 1983; ROY, 1991). For this reason, Moroccan coasts are very productive with plentiful halieutic resour-

* Laboratory Aquamar, Faculty of Sciences of Agadir, Ibn Zuhr University, Agadir, Morocco.
Corresponding author: Moukrim, Abdellatif. Laboratoire Aquamar fac et université moukrim@uiz.ac.ma

ces. Among these resources, molluscs constitute an important ecological and economic group. Along the Moroccan coasts, mussels are represented by two species: the Mediterranean mussel *Mytilus galloprovincialis* and the African mussel *Perna perna*. They both play a crucial role in the socioeconomic life of the local populations and sustainable aquaculture projects are currently developed, particularly in southern Morocco. On the other hand, research on these two mussel species has focused mainly on the North and Centre of Morocco (NACIRI, 1997; SHAFFEE, 1992; ID HALLA, 1997, 2006; BOUHAIMI ET AL., 2000), and not on the southern coastal ecosystems.

The Bay of Mirleft (Sidi Ifni province, South Morocco) is known for the abundance of mussels that are mainly used by the local population. Currently, interest in the development of aquaculture projects is growing; however, no scientific data are available on the life cycle of the mussels living in this area. This type of information is important for setting up strategies for sustainable ecosystem management that also meet the expectations of the local populations.

Therefore, the aim of this study was to determine the growth, reproduction and population dynamics of the mussel species *M. galloprovincialis* and *P. perna* in three representative sites of this ecosystem.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Study sites

Three coastal sites in Mirleft Bay were selected for this study (Fig. 1):

i) Grizim (29°38'06" N - 10°00'38" W), located 10 km North of the Mirleft resort. It has a rocky coastline and a pebble beach, with moderate wave action.

ii) Tabougricht (29°35'19"N - 10°02'43"W), located at the North entrance of the Mirleft resort. It is a rocky area, characterized by intense wave action and relative inaccessibility that limits mussel harvesting by the local people.

iii) Sidi Mohammed Ben Abdellah site (29°34'24" N - 010°03'18"W) is close to a beach frequented by tourists. It is mainly a rocky area where mussels can be easily harvested at low tide.

Sample collection and handling

At each site, two sets of samples of *M. galloprovincialis* and *P. perna* were collected at low tide each month, between March 2009 and April 2010. Sixty animals of similar size were used for the histological evaluation of reproducing animals and for sex determination.

Histological analysis of animals was carried out according to the method described by LUBET (1959) in which sexual cycle of mussels is divided in seven stages of maturation (Table I, Figures 2-3), which are the basis for calculating the gonadal index (GI):

$$GI = [(nb \text{ ind stages I and IIID}) + (nb \text{ ind stages I, II, IIIB, IIIC}) \times 2 + (nb \text{ ind stages IIIA}) \times 3] / \text{Tot ind tested}$$

RESULTS

Reproductive cycle

All stages described by Lubet (1959), including the stage of sexual rest, were observed in mussels collected at the three study sites (Figure 4).

For *P. perna*, animals that reached stage I and II were found at the three sites during the entire study period, except in April at Grizim and Tabougricht. Mature animals (stage IIIA) were present throughout the study period, except between September and November 2009 (samples collected at Grizim) and May, October and November 2009 (samples from the Sidi Mohammed ben Abdellah site). Stage IIIB mussels (release of gametes) were present throughout the study period (with the exception of September) with two spawning periods (March-April and October-December) at the three sites. For *M. galloprovincialis*, stage 0 animals were only found at Grizim between June and September 2009, with a peak in July (18%). Stage I and II mussels were

Figure 1. Map showing the three study sites.
 Figura 1. Mapa mostrando las tres localidades de estudio.

Table I. Description of the different stages of the reproductive cycle of mussels, following LUBET (1959).

Tabla I. Descripción de las diferentes etapas del ciclo reproductivo de los mejillones, según LUBET (1959).

Stage	Nom	Description
Stage 0	Sexual rest	Accumulation of reserves established by adipogranulose cells and vesicular cells. The mantle looks seamless and transparent, sex is indeterminate.
Stage I	Resumption of genital activity	Early stage of gametogenesis.
Stage II	Gametogenesis	Much of the mantle is occupied by the follicles. In the female, the ovules continue to grow by accumulating yolk, while in the male, the follicles appear as a broad band centripetal spermatogonia, spermatocytes and spermatids with some free sperm in the lumen.
Stage IIIA	Genital maturity, emission of gametes	Follicles occupying the entire surface of gonadal tissue. In males, a narrow band of gametogenetic products appears in the direction of the opening of the follicles. Spermatozooids are arranged in strips. In females, the oocytes are well developed and have a polygonal shape due to their high density in the follicles.
Stage IIIB	Emission of gametes	Emission of gametes may be total or partial. A considerable number of follicles are emptied and contain only residual gametes. The density of follicles and spermatozooids decreases.
Stage IIIC	Restoration of the gonad	Stage of gamete renewal before renewed spawning in the same cycle. In males, there appears a band corresponding to the early gametic stages. In females, young follicular oocytes attached to the periphery are abundant.
Stage IIID	Cessation of genital activity and reabsorption	Cessation of genital activity, follicular degeneration and phagocytosis of unspawned gametes by amœbocytes. Cellular debris often observed, the animal was again forced to resting stage.

Figure 2. Different stages of the reproductive cycle in *P. perna* females collected at Grizim. A: stage I (resumption of genital activity); B: stage II (oogenesis); C: stage IIIA (genital maturity); D: stage IIIB (gamete release); E: stage IIIC (gonad restoration); F: stage IIID (ceasing of genital activity and reabsorption). Abbreviations, fp: primary follicle; tg: germinal tissue; tc: connective tissue.

Figura 2. Distintas etapas del ciclo reproductor de *Perna perna bembra* recolectada en Grizim. A: estadio I (reanudación de la actividad genital); B: estadio II (ovogénesis); C: estadio IIIA (madurez genital); D: estadio IIIB (liberación de gametos); E: estadio IIIC (restauración de la gónada); F: estadio IIID (cese de la actividad genital y reabsorción). Abreviaturas, fp: folículo primario; tg: tejido germinal; tc: tejido conectivo.

found throughout the study period. Similarly, stage IIIA and IIIB animals were present during most of the study period, with a first peak at the three sites in March-April 2009 and 2010 and

a second peak at Tabougricht and Sidi Mohammed ben Abdellah.

The gonad index (Figure 5) for *M. galloprovincialis* showed fairly stable values in March and April. The index

Figura 3. Different stages of the reproductive cycle of *M. galloprovincialis* males harvested at Grizim. A: stage I (resumption of genital activity); B: stage II (spermatogenesis); C: stage IIIA (genital maturity); D: stage IIIB (gamete release); E: stage IIIC (gonad restoration); F: stage IIID (ceasing of genital activity and reabsorption). Abbreviations, fp: primary follicle; tg: germinal tissue; tc: connective tissue.
 Figura 3. Las Diferentes etapas del ciclo reproductivo de *Mytilus galloprovincialis* macho recolectado en Grizim. A: estadio I (reanudación de la actividad genital); B: estadio II (espermatogénesis); C: estadio IIIA (madurez genital); D: estadio IIIB (liberación de gametos); E: estadio IIIC (restauración de la gónada); F: estadio IIID (cese de la actividad genital y reabsorción). Abreviaturas, fp: folículo primario; tg: tejido germinal; tc: tejido conectivo.

slightly decreased in May to increase again in September, a partial egg laying period. Similarly, the gonad index in *P. perna* also was relatively stable (values between 1.5 and 2.7 in 2009). It slightly

decreased in May and August and increased again in December 2009 (2.2 to 2.5). From January to April 2010, the gonad index slightly decreased and remained stable at values between 2 and 2.2.

Figure 4. Frequency of stages of gametogenesis in *Perna perna* and *Mytilus galloprovincialis* of sites Grizim, Tabougricht and Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdallah.

Figura 4. Frecuencia de las etapas de la gametogénesis de *Perna perna* y *Mytilus galloprovincialis* en las localidades de Grizim, Tabougricht y Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdallah.

Sex ratio

The analysis of the histological results showed that the sex ratio in *Perna perna* was in favor of males at the three sites, whereas it was the opposite for *M. galloprovincialis*, except at the Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdallah (Table II).

DISCUSSION

The data collected during this study provide information on the reproductive cycle, growth, recruitment and population dynamics of the two mussel species (*M. galloprovincialis* and *P. perna*) cohabiting in the Mirleft region (South

Morocco), and constitute a scientific basis for any development of this resource.

Our results show that the two species are characterized by a reproductive cycle with a small percentage of individuals in the stage of sexual rest (stage 0) at all three sites. This is in agreement with the findings by ID HALLA (1997) for mussels in Agadir Bay. However, in northern regions of Morocco, a much higher percentage of mussels in resting stage was observed (SHAFEE, 1992).

The reproductive cycle of mussels in the Mirleft region was also characterized by the presence of two spawning

Figure 5. Gonad index evolution in *Mytilus galloprovincialis* (above) and *Perna perna* (below) in Grizim, Tabougricht and Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdellah sites.

Figura 5. Evolución del índice gonádico en *Mytilus galloprovincialis* (arriba) y *Perna perna* (abajo) en las localidades de Grizim, Tabougricht y Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdellah.

Table II. Number of individuals by sex of *Perna perna* (Pp) and *Mytilus galloprovincialis* (Mg) collected at the three sites.

Tabla II. Número de individuos por sexo de *Perna perna* (Pp) y *Mytilus galloprovincialis* (Mg) obtenidos en las tres localidades.

Sites	Sex	<i>Perna perna</i>	<i>Mytilus galloprovincialis</i>
Grizim	male	531	386
	female	295	370
	resting stage	14	24
Tabougricht	male	436	413
	female	378	398
	resting stage	26	29
Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdellah	male	472	447
	female	337	334
	resting stage	31	59

periods (stage IIIB): between March and April (both in 2009 and in 2010) and between September and December 2009. Other authors have reported several intermittent spawning periods for *M. galloprovincialis* and *P. perna* in the bay of Agadir (ID HALLA ET AL., 1997; BENOMAR, 2005), in the South Atlantic coasts (CAYRE, 1981) and in the South African coast (LASIAK, 1986). However, the months in which spawning occurs are slightly different among sites. This is probably related to changes in climatic conditions, geographical latitude (SCHURINK AND GRIFFITHS, 1991) as well as in biotic and abiotic factors to which these species must adapt (VELEZ AND EPIFANIO, 1981; GRIFFITHS AND GRIFFITHS, 1987). Indeed, egg production in mussels is often triggered by variations in the amount of food present in the water and abrupt changes in the water temperature. According to several authors, the nutritional factor is essential for maintaining a good balance between energy reserves and energy required for gametogenesis (LUBET, ALOUI AND KARANAUKHOVA, 1986; HICKS, TUNNEL & MCMAHON, 2001; JARAMILLO ET AL., 1993).

Recruitments were observed throughout the study period, with peaks in summer. This suggests that egg laying might have been favored by the increasing sea water temperature (SCHURINK AND GRIFFITHS, 1991).

Besides surface currents (Canary current), the Mirleft coastline is subject to nutrient-rich coastal upwelling. These cold bottom waters are the main source of nutrient enrichment for coastal

ecosystems (BAINBRIDGE, 1960; BINET, 1983; ROY, 1991; AGOUMI & ORBI, 1992), thus favoring marine life development. Coastal upwelling along the Moroccan coast is seasonal. It starts in February/March and peaks in July-August at Agadir Bay (AGOUMI & ORBI, 1992; ID HALLA, 2006) and the north of Morocco (WOOSTER, BAKUN & MCLAIN, 1976). This influences the mussel seasonal biological rhythms. It was reported that upwelling intensity is correlated with spawning, which is also linked to water warming in spring and summer (ID HALLA, 2006). This could explain why recruitment, which was observed throughout the study period, peaked in summer, suggesting that important spawning was promoted by higher sea water temperatures (Schurink and Griffiths (1991) and upwelling-induced nutrient richness (ASKEW, 1972; UTTING, 1986; URRUTIA ET AL., 1999). These nutrients allow the development of phytoplankton which is at the base of the marine food chain.

CONCLUSION

Our study shows that the Bay of Mirleft environment is suitable for the development of mussel farming. Specifically, its waters are rich in nutrients due to the upwelling and reproductive cycle with hardly any biological rest and abundant recruitment. Nevertheless, additional studies are required to identify the most appropriate farming sites and to investigate the potential markets for such production.

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